

3D Microstructure Visualization of SiC Particle Reinforced Al Matrix Composites by X-Ray Synchrotron Tomography

F.A. Silva*, J.J. Williams, and N. Chawla
School of Materials
Fulton School of Engineering
Arizona State University
Tempe, AZ 85287-8706
e-mail: Nikhilesh.Chawla@asu.edu

B.R. Müller, M.P. Hentschel and P.D. Portella
Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing (BAM)
Unter den Eichen 87, D-12200 Berlin, Germany

* Current address: Institute of Construction Materials, Technical University of Dresden, 01062 Dresden, Germany

SUMMARY

Microstructural aspects of composites such as particle size, shape, and distribution play important roles in deformation behavior. 3D visualization of porosity and Fe-rich inclusions in three dimensions is critical to a thorough understanding of fatigue resistance of metal matrix composites (MMC) because cracks often initiate at these defects. In this paper we have used X-ray synchrotron tomography to visualize and quantify the morphology and size distribution of pores and Fe-rich inclusions in a SiC particle reinforced 2080 Al alloy composite. The 3D data sets can also be used for image-based finite element simulations to predict the onset and evolution of damage.

Keywords: synchrotron radiation, X-ray tomography, X-ray refraction, Analyser Based Imaging, MMC, fatigue.

INTRODUCTION

The design and development of high performance materials requires a thorough understanding and careful control of microstructure and its effect on mechanical properties. In order to understand the fatigue performance of metal matrix composites (MMC), it is important to investigate the size, morphological characteristics, and distribution of inclusions and porosity. Current analytical and numerical techniques simplify the heterogeneous microstructure of multiphase materials, making modelling and analysis more straightforward, but failing to accurately predict the effective properties and local damage behavior which are inherently dependent on microstructure [1]. It follows that accurate prediction of macroscopic deformation behavior and modelling of localized damage mechanisms can only be accomplished by capturing the microstructure of the material as a basis for the model. For metal matrix composites it has been shown that while 2D micromechanical models are able to capture the anisotropy in deformation behavior induced by anisotropy in particle orientation, the 3D

microstructure-based FEM accurately represents the alignment, aspect ratio, and distribution of the particles [1].

Serial sectioning techniques such as serial mechanical polishing [2-6] or focused ion beam (FIB) milling [7] followed by optical microscopy and image reconstruction has been used for 3D visualization and FEM modelling. While serial sectioning is a powerful technique for generating virtual 3D microstructures, it presents some drawbacks. In particular, the sample preparation process is time consuming and destructive. An alternative is x-ray tomography [5,8] which eliminates cross-sectioning, and allows for superior resolution, and image quality with minimal sample preparation. 3D image visualization by x-ray tomography has been successfully performed in Pb-free solder joints [8], powder metallurgy steels [5], and metal matrix composites [9-11].

Synchrotron radiation has been used for x-ray tomography [9] and holotomography [10,11] in MMCs in order to visualize its microstructure. Babout et al. [9] clearly visualized the microstructure of MMC (Ti/SiCf) at a suitable resolution. Void growth and coalescence has also been investigated through x-ray synchrotron tomography [12]. It was shown the strong effect of macroscopic necking on the coalescence path and that increased material strength and the nucleation of secondary voids resulted in greatly reduced coalescence strains. 3D fatigue crack growth has been investigated using *in-situ* synchrotron x-ray tomography in the interior of an Al-Mg-Si alloy [13]. Three-dimensional fatigue crack geometries and their development have been quantified as a function of applied loads. *In situ* observations of inhomogeneous deformation in semi-solid aluminium alloys were also performed demonstrating that deformation of a semi-solid material is highly inhomogeneous and the solid and liquid phases re-organise themselves [14].

In the present work we showed that the microstructure of SiC particle reinforced 2080 Al can be visualized and quantified by x-ray synchrotron tomography using absorption and refraction techniques. 3D models were obtained by re-construction of 2D images using in-house software and commercially available software. The size and distribution of Fe-rich inclusions and pores was visualized and quantified. This type of analysis will be invaluable for predicting and understanding the effect of defects on the fatigue response of MMCs, by incorporating the 3D virtual data sets into numerical models (finite element models, for example).

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Processing and Testing

The Al and alloy powders used in this study were gas atomized (Valimet Inc.). A SiC abrasive grade powder (Saint-Gobain) was used as the particle reinforcement. The alloy powder consisted of a mixture of pure Al powder, Al-50 wt% Cu prealloyed powder, and Al-50 wt% Mg prealloyed powder. The prealloyed powders were used for enhanced sinterability and compositional homogeneity in the matrix. The composite contained 20 vol.% SiC and a bulk alloy composition of 3.7 wt% Cu, 1.8 wt% Mg, and

balance of Al, consistent with the composition of 2080 Al alloy. A schematic of the sinter-forging process is shown in Figure 1. The powder mixture was blended in a V-cone blender and cold compacted at a pressure of 480 MPa. The powder compact was then sintered in a N₂ atmosphere at 565 °C for 60 min to achieve partial densification, followed by closed-die forging at 482 °C to achieve near-full density (Metaldyne Inc.). The nominal total strain achieved during forging, through the thickness of the perform, was approximately 25%. More information on the processing and mechanical properties of these specific composites can be found elsewhere [15].

Figure 1. Schematic of sinter-forging process [15].

After processing the MMC specimen was subjected to fatigue loading. Axial fatigue was carried out in force control mode using a sinusoidal waveform, R-ratio ($\sigma_{\min}/\sigma_{\max}$) of -1, and a frequency of 40 Hz. The sample was loaded to a stress amplitude of 190 MPa ($\sigma_{\max}=95$ MPa) on a precision aligned servohydraulic load frame, in order to minimize bending strains, with a 100 kN load cell.

X-Ray Synchrotron Tomography

The x-ray synchrotron tomography was performed in SiC particle reinforced Al matrix composites previously subjected to fatigue load as explained previously. Samples were sectioned using electric discharge machining (EDM) into a square cross section of 1 mm x 1 mm as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Sectioning of pre-fatigued sample for x-ray synchrotron tomography experiment.

The X-ray synchrotron tomography experiments were performed at the *BAMline* in Bessy II, a third generation synchrotron light source located in Berlin, Germany. Absorption (based on density of the phases) and refraction (sensitive to inner surfaces and interfaces) tomography scans were performed. A schematic of the *BAMline* is shown in Figure 3. Monochromatic synchrotron light of 20 KeV was attained by a double crystal monochromator (DCM with Si(111) crystals) and used for the present investigation. Slits are positioned upstream (aperture) and downstream of the monochromator as well as in the experimental hutch. The synchrotron beam transmitted by the sample was converted with a scintillator into visible light. By use of microscope optics this luminescence image was then projected onto a CCD Camera. The detector system was optimised by using the scintillating material LuAG:Eu ($\text{Lu}_3\text{Al}_5\text{O}_{12}$ europium doped, thickness 20 μm). The optical system consisted of a CCD camera with 2048×2048 pixels, a Nikon objective (1:1.8 $f = 180$ mm) and a TV Heligon (1:1.2 $f = 21$ mm). A resolution of about 2 μm was obtained. A scan was performed by a 180° rotation along a vertical axis resulting in 541 two dimensional (2D) radiographs. The source-to-sample distance at the *BAMline* is 37 m (see Fig. 3) and the source size is 3.5 μm . For a typical sample to detector distance of 10mm the image blurring resulting from the finite source size has no influence on high resolution imaging (e.g., by penumbral blurring). More information on the *BAMline* can be found elsewhere [16, 17].

Figure 3. Layout of the X-ray beam path at *BAMline* (top: side view, bottom: top view) [16].

The 2D radiographs obtained were used to re-construct the volume of the samples using in-house softwares developed at BAM and post-processed using Image J (ImageJ, Bethesda, MD) and Mimics (Mimics, Materialise, Ann Arbor, MI).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The microstructure of the as-processed composites consists of the highly angular SiC particles, as well as Fe-rich inclusions and residual porosity. The Fe-rich inclusions arise as impurities in powder processing. Figure 4 shows the as-processed microstructure of the particle SiC reinforced Al matrix composite. The SEM micrograph shows the SiC particles and Fe-rich inclusions. The SiC particles appear to be relatively randomly distributed.

Figure 4. SEM micrograph of as processed SiC particle reinforced Al.

SiC particle reinforced Al composites were inspected by refraction and absorption x-ray synchrotron tomography after fatigue loading. Figure 5 shows a 2D re-constructed tomography slice of a MMC specimen that failed at 8,199,333 cycles. The fracture surface is shown at the top of the micrographs. Both techniques, refraction and absorption, are complementary for analysing desired features. Nevertheless, a better contrast between SiC particles and Al matrix and for porosity visualization was obtained in the absorption mode. The obtained reconstructed images show the following features: SiC particles, pores, and Fe-rich inclusions. The Fe-rich inclusions appeared in both refraction and absorption techniques. Since refraction mode is more sensitive to inner surfaces and interfaces a brighter contrast is observed for the fracture surface and for some pores (circles 2 and 3 in Figure 5).

Figure 5. 2D reconstructed tomographic slice of particle SiC reinforced Al matrix composite subjected to fatigue load: (a) absorption and (b) refraction. The techniques are complementary for analysing desired features.

3D visualization of pores and Fe-rich inclusion was obtained by post-processing the tomography images in Mimics (Mimics, Materialise, Ann Arbor, MI). This type of visualization allows the computation of volume, size, and distribution of the observed features. Furthermore, more detailed information about the geometry of Fe-rich inclusions and porosity can be observed. For instance it can be observed that the Fe-rich inclusion in Figure 6a presents an irregular shape with a hole in its upper side. It can be also seen that the pores (Figure 6b) are uniformly distributed inside the sample and they present an inclination throughout the different planes. This irregular and somewhat anisotropic morphology of the pores can be due to the forging conditions.

Figure 6. 3D visualization of (a) Fe-rich inclusions and (b) pores in particle SiC reinforced Al matrix composites.

Quantitative analysis was performed to characterize the size, volume, and distribution of the Fe-rich inclusions and pores in the MMC. These are shown in Figure 7 and Table 1. A lower volume (0.07 %) of Fe-rich inclusions with higher frequency for volumes below $1000 \mu\text{m}^3$ was observed. The pores had a similar frequency distribution but with higher volume (0.23 %).

Chawla et al. [18] have shown that the fatigue resistance of particulate MMCs depends on a variety of factors, including reinforcement particle volume fraction, particle size, matrix microstructure, the presence of inclusions or defects that arise from processing, and testing environment. Factors affecting the matrix microstructure include size, shape, and spacing of precipitates, grain size, and non-reinforcement inclusions (such as Fe-rich inclusions that are formed during processing). Therefore, the reduction in fraction and size of inclusions greatly increases the fatigue life of MMCs. The low frequency of Fe-rich inclusions and pores observed for volumes above $2000 \mu\text{m}^3$ are beneficial for the fatigue performance of MMCs.

Figure 7. Frequency distribution of Fe-rich inclusion and pores in particle SiC reinforced Al composite.

It has been shown by Chawla et al. [15] that the presence of the Fe-rich inclusions in MMCs are a weak point where cracks initiate and propagate during fatigue (see Figure 8). The reduction of these inclusions are important to increase the fatigue life of metal matrix composites and the use of a high resolution x-ray synchrotron tomography is an important tool for quantification and morphology characterization of inclusions and pores. The use of the 3D tomographic images in a finite element code to predict and to better understand the role of inclusions and pores in the fatigue behaviour of MMCs is the next step in this research.

Figure 8. SEM micrograph showing fatigue crack initiation and growth in MMC. Note that the crack initiated in a Fe-rich inclusion [15].

Table 1. Quantitative analysis of Fe-rich inclusions and pores in particle SiC reinforced Al matrix composites.

Feature	Volume (%)	Average Size (μm^3)	Median Size (μm^3)	Max Size (μm^3)	Skewness
Inclusion	0.07	2,926	561	44,972	3.3
Pore	0.23	585	361	12,326	3.6

CONCLUSIONS

X-ray synchrotron tomography have been used for 3D visualization of the microstructure in particles SiC reinforced Al matrix composites. The following conclusions can be drawn from the present research:

- X-ray synchrotron tomography is an important non-destructive tool for 3D microstructure visualization in MMCs resulting in images with enhanced contrast.
- Absorption and refraction x-ray synchrotron tomography are complementary techniques. A better contrast between SiC particles and Al matrix and for the visualization of pores was obtained under absorption.

- Fe-rich inclusions and pores were morphologically characterized and quantified. The volume fraction of inclusions and pores was 0.07 % and 0.23 %, respectively. Their frequency was below 1% for volumes above 2000 μm^3 .

- The effect of Fe-rich inclusions on the fatigue response has been demonstrated. Using this technique, one can incorporate 3D virtual data sets into numerical models to elucidate the effect of the defects on local stress state and to predict the onset of crack initiation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

FAS is grateful for financial support from BAM to carry out this work during a one month stay at BAM. NC is very thankful to BAM and Dr. P. Portella for financial support during a sabbatical stay at BAM to begin a collaboration that resulted in this work.

References

1. N. Chawla and K.K. Chawla. Microstructure-based modelling of the deformation behaviour of particle reinforced metal matrix composites. *Journal of Materials Science* 41 (2006) 913-925.
2. M.A. Dudek and N. Chawla. Three-dimensional (3D) Microstructure Visualization of LaSn_3 Intermetallics in a Novel Sn-rich Rare-Earth Containing Solder. *Materials Characterization* 59 (2008) 1364-1368.
3. R.S. Sidhu and N. Chawla. Three-dimensional microstructure characterization of Ag_3Sn intermetallics in Sn-rich solder by serial sectioning. *Materials Characterization* 52 (2004) 225– 230.
4. N. Chawla, V.V. Ganesh, and B. Wunsch. Three-dimensional (3D) microstructure visualization and finite element modeling of the mechanical behavior of SiC particle reinforced aluminum composites. *Scripta Materialia* 51 (2004) 161–165.
5. N. Chawla, J.J. Williams, X. Deng, and C. McClimon. Three dimensional (3D) characterization and modelling of porosity in powder metallurgy (P/M) steels. *International Journal of Powder Metallurgy* 45 (2009) 19-27.
6. N. Chawla, R.S. Sidhu, and V.V. Ganesh. Three-dimensional visualization and microstructure-based modelling of deformation in particle-reinforced composites. *Acta Materialia* 54 (2006) 1541-1548.
7. A.J. Kubis, G.J. Shiflet, and R. Hull. Focused ion-beam tomography. *Metall. Mater. Trans.* 35 (2004) 1935-1943.

8. M. Dudek, L. Hunter, S. Kranz, J.J. Williams, S.H. Lau, and N. Chawla. Three-dimensional (3D) visualization of reflow porosity and modelling of deformation in Pb-free solder joints. *Journal of Electronic Materials* (2009), in press.
9. L. Babout, E. Maire, J.-Y. Buffière, and R. Fougères. Recent results on 3D characterisation of microstructure and damage of metal matrix composites and a metallic foam using X-ray tomography *Acta Mater.* 49 (2001) 2055.
10. A. Borbély, F.F. Csikor, S. Zabler, P. Cloetens, and H. Biermann. Three-dimensional characterization of the microstructure of a metal–matrix composite by holotomography. *Materials Science and Engineering A* 367 (2004) 40–50.
11. P. Kenesei, H. Biermann, and A. Borbély. Structure–property relationship in particle reinforced metal–matrix composites based on holotomography. *Scripta Materialia* 53 (2005) 787–791.
12. A. Weck, D.S. Wilkinson, E. Maire, and H. Toda. Visualization by X-ray tomography of void growth and coalescence leading to fracture in model materials. *Acta Materialia* 56 (2008) 2919–2928.
13. H. Zhang, H. Toda, P.C. Qu, Y. Sakaguchi, M. Kobayashi, K. Uesugi, and Y. Suzuki. Three-dimensional fatigue crack growth behavior in an aluminum alloy investigated with in situ high-resolution synchrotron X-ray microtomography. *Acta Materialia* (2009), in press, doi:10.1016/j.actamat.2009.03.036.
14. S. Terzi, L. Salvo, M. Suéry, N. Limodin, J. Adrien, E. Maire, Y. Pannier, M. Bornert, D. Bernard, M. Felberbaum, M. Rappaz, and E. Boller. In situ X-ray tomography observation of inhomogeneous deformation in semisolid aluminum alloys. *Scripta Materialia* (2009), in press, doi: 10.1016/j.scriptamat.2009.04.041
15. N. Chawla, J.J. Williams, and R. Saha. Mechanical behavior and microstructure characterization of sinter-forged SiC particle reinforced aluminum matrix composites. *Journal of Light Metals* 2 (2002) 215–227.
16. A. Rack, S. Zabler, B.R. Müller, H. Riesemeier, G. Weidemann, A. Lange, J. Goebbels, M. Hentschel, and W. Gerner. High resolution synchrotron-based radiography and tomography using hard X-rays at the BAMline (BESSY II). *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A* 586 (2008) 327–344.
17. W. Gerner, M.P. Hentschel, B.R. Müller, H. Riesemeier, M. Krumrey, G. Ulm, W. Diete, U. Klein, and R. Frahm. *BAMline*: the first hard X-ray beamline at BESSY II. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A* 467–468 (2001) 703–706.
18. N. Chawla and Y-L Shen. Mechanical behaviour of particle reinforced metal matrix composites. *Advanced Engineering Materials* 3 (2001) 357-370.